

Characteristics of the Harrod-Domar model of economic growth

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Abstract

By the second half of the 50s of the 20th century, interest in the problem of economic growth increased, and the works of a number of economists (R. Harrod, E. Domar, J. Robinson, R. Solow, etc.) devoted to it began to appear. This is due to the inability of the old classical theory, which often denies economic dynamics, to meet the real requirements of modern economic development. High economic growth is now commonplace in developed countries.

Keywords: Economic growth, model, capital stock only function, technical conditions of production, labor and capital, national income

The Harrod-Domar model of economic growth began to emerge in the second half of the 1950s. One of the simple models for determining the rate of economic growth was developed by the English economist R.F. Harrod (1900–1978) and American economist E.D. It is a model developed by Domarlar (born in 1914). The model they proposed is consistent and is commonly referred to as the Harrod-Domar model. This model is based on two conditions: 1) the growth of national income is only a function of the capital stock, all other factors affecting the increase of capital return (increase in employment, level of use of scientific and technical achievements, improvement of production organization) are not taken into account. Therefore, the Harrod and Domar model is a one-factor model. At the current capital capacity, it is assumed that the demand for capital depends only on the growth rate of national income; 2) capital capacity does not depend on the ratio of prices of production factors, but is determined only by the technical conditions of production.

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In Keynesian theory, investment is the main factor of economic growth. Investments play an important role in the considered model of economic growth: on the one hand, they increase capital accumulation, and on the other hand, they increase production capacity. Investments are variable, with the help of which economic growth can be regulated. 149 Contribution of funds to national income is considered constant. Equality of savings S and investments I is one of the necessary conditions for sustainable economic growth. If the savings exceed the investments, then there will be excess reserves, the equipment will not be fully used, and unemployment will increase. This situation leads to a decrease in economic growth. If investment exceeds savings, it can cause the economy to "strain" and cause prices to rise. The problem is that the relationship between savings and investment does not look the same in the short-run ("static") and long-run ("dynamic") periods. In the short term, savings and investments are equal in terms of the final amount. In the long term, a different situation is observed.

Funds allocated today (supply) must correspond to investments planned for tomorrow (demand). Matching current supply and expected demand, coordinating today's savings and tomorrow's investment is a huge challenge. If we do not take into account considerations of the economic situation, then in the long-term period, on the one hand, real savings and expected investments are assumed, and on the other hand, attention is paid not to average indicators, but to growing indicators, final (growing) factors, under the influence of which investments are organized. The one-factor Harrod-Domar model serves as an auxiliary tool aimed at solving the problem of economic growth in the long run. This model helps to reveal the nature of interactions in the dynamics, to visualize them more clearly. The equation of economic growth in dynamics. The Harrod-Domar formula has the following form: $Y = S / K$, or $Y \cdot K = S$, where: Y is the rate of economic growth, S is the contribution of savings to the national income, K is the ratio of capital to the created product (capital capacity coefficient). It can be concluded from the given equation that the

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rate of economic growth is equal to the division of the contribution of savings in national income Y by the coefficient of capital capacity S divided by K . The expression $Y \cdot K$ represents the contribution of net investment in national income. Why is such a relationship considered? 1. The ratio of net savings to national income, S . The greater the contribution of net savings, the greater the amount of investment in general. The higher their growth, the higher the rate of economic growth: there is a direct relationship between the growth of investments and the rate of economic growth. 2. The ratio of capital capacity, that is, the ratio of capital to products, K . The growth rate is related to capital capacity. The higher the capital capacity 150, the lower the rate of economic growth. Conversely, the lower the level of capital capacity (due to technical progress, structural changes), the higher the growth rate. There is an inverse relationship between the capital capacity ratio and the rate of economic growth.

Let's see how the Harrod-Domar formula works in the case of the United States. The growth rate is determined according to the growth of the capital investment and its efficiency (return). The growth rate of employment is assumed to be the same as the growth rate of capital. For simplicity and clarity, the numbers are given in the form of a whole. US national income is 4000 billion. dollars, the national capital is 12,000 bln. dollar (1988) as equal. Net investment, corresponding to the amount of net saving C , has been equal to 9% for a long time, or 0.09% of national income. This is 360 billion. dollar is $(0.09 \cdot 4000)$. In the form of the ratio of all capital to output (national income), the capital capacity coefficient is equal to $K: 3$ (12000 : 4000). If we express these quantities in the Harrod-Domar model, we get the following result: $Y = 0.09 : 3 = 0.03$ After knowing the initial economic parameters, it is possible to forecast the future growth rate. Of course, the real growth rate may differ from the average figure resulting from such a calculation. In fact, economic growth is formed under the influence of other factors that the model we have considered does not take into account. In reality, economic growth depends on

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the phase of the economic cycle, the structure of investments, the use of technological advances, and other factors. What will be the economic growth in dynamics? If the share of savings in national income, C , is kept constant and the capital ratio remains unchanged, the economy can grow at the calculated rate (3 percent growth). The problem of achieving equilibrium in dynamics. There is no automatic mechanism that eliminates the deviation of S and K from the "norm" (in our example, $S = 0.09$, $K = 3$), which ensures a proportional growth rate in the economy. The capital capacity ratio can deviate above or below the "norm" in a short period of time. The normative value of this coefficient is the same under conditions of full employment, but different under conditions of non-full employment. In conditions of full employment, the coefficient of capital capacity is much lower ($K = 2.85$), because the capital is more full and intensively used, and as a result, there is a shortage of tools, machine tools, and raw materials. The opposite situation occurs when there is no full employment (the coefficient of capital capacity K is, say, 3.15). The paradox is that when the growth rate is high, it is necessary to lower it a little, the capital capacity ratio accelerates the growth rate even more. During a recession, there is a shortage of production capacity (the Y/C ratio decreases) and the rate of economic growth slows down even more. Therefore, the market mechanism itself, instead of stabilizing the developing system, keeps it shaking.

According to the Harrod-Domar model, when speaking about the dynamic equilibrium conditions, as mentioned above, it is assumed that real savings and estimated investments are equal. It is expressed in the Harrod formula: $Y_w \cdot K_r = S$, Here, $Y_w \cdot K_r$ are the quantities required for dynamic balance; K_p – amount of required capital ratio (capital capacity); Y_w – guaranteed growth rate. Due to the differences between "guaranteed" and real growth rates - due to changes in the contribution of savings in national income and the coefficient of capital capacity, the equilibrium in dynamics is not regularly achieved, but periodically through errors and corrections. The "guaranteed" growth rate is the growth rate that ensures a

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dynamic balance between real savings and required investments (Harrod R. K. teorii ekonomicheskoy dynamiki. M., 1959.) The real growth rate is the real growth of national income in one year: $Y = \Delta V / V$ Equilibrium is achieved only if the "guaranteed" growth rate is equal to the expected growth rate of national income. If the expected growth rate does not match the "guaranteed" growth rate, then the actual growth rate will deviate significantly from the "norm". Because of this deviation and instability, the actual growth rate will always deviate from the "guaranteed" growth rate. For this reason, according to Harrod, fluctuations in the economic situation are inevitable. Since the "guaranteed" rate of growth in the countries of the market economy, according to the New Keynesians, cannot always be achieved automatically, they show that it is necessary for the state to organize the economy in order to achieve a dynamic balance. Conditions for sustainable growth. In the Keynesian analysis of economic growth, the problem of investment is central. One of the goals of the Harrod Domar model is to extend this analysis. This model helps to determine not the state of economic growth in the short term (for example, within one production), but what the economic growth curve will be in the long 152 period. The model helps to show what conditions are necessary to achieve sustained, uniform economic growth. From the analysis of American economists, the necessity of a number of preconditions emerges: - economic growth requires not only the support of the level of current investments and state capital investments, but also their increase; increased investment is seen as a new driving force for economic growth; - ensuring the optimal ratio between the growth of today's savings and the expected growth of investments: $S = i; I$ - it is necessary to always balance demand (stimulation of investments) and supply (gross product that can be created under conditions of full employment and use of all production factors); - the balance between the increase in supply and the increase in demand is established on the basis of the decisive effect of investments that ensure the increase of fixed capital.

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